

The CARESSES Ontology for Socially Assistive Robotics

Namespace Document, 17 June 2019

This version:

[CARESSES Ontology_ \(owl\)](#)

Latest version:

[CARESSES Ontology_ \(owl\)](#)

Status:

Work in progress

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Introduction

Socially assistive robots use social interaction as a mean in itself for enhancing health and psychological well-being of older people motivating users to maintain a healthy lifestyle, guiding them in the execution of daily activities and providing companionship. In this context, endowing a socially assistive robot with cultural knowledge makes it more aware of culture-related preferences, traditions and needs, and allows it to behave more competently, tuning its behaviour to meet the customs and expectations of the user. As ageing populations across the world are placing health and social care systems under pressure, culturally competent robots can assist human caregivers in some tasks, thus helping to reduce the pressure in hospitals and care homes and improve care delivery at home.

[As part of a joint effort towards the development of a culturally competent robot](#) for elderly care, experts in Transcultural Nursing have led the development of guidelines defining the behaviour and functionalities of a culturally competent robot for older people, linking cultural knowledge and perceptual information to actions and utterances. These guidelines have an impact upon the following main areas:

- **Goals.** The user always has the last word in choosing what the robot should do for her. However, the robot might proactively make suggestions, and some of them might depend on cultural factors. What activity should the robot suggest the user to engage in before lunch? Cooking – and what menu?, praying – and how? What will the user

most likely want to be reminded of? Social or cultural events – and which ones?, TV shows?

- **Actions and their parameters.** Different cultures may use different actions to convey the same concept. How should the robot greet the user? Waving, bowing, or with a Namaste? What volume would the user be comfortable with? What distance while interacting?
- **Norms.** Behaviours which are common in one culture might be unacceptable in others. Are there areas of the house that should be off-limits for the robot? Does the answer depend on the time of the day? What is the user likely to consider as private?
- **Topics of conversation.** Different cultures might have different histories, customs and traditions, which influence the lifestyle of people. What are the topics a user might like to talk about? Is she interested in sports, movies, politics or social activities? And if so, which sports, which types of movies could the robot suggest? Topics of conversation are also those activities in which the robot might assist the user, independently from any physical assistance it might also provide. Could the user be interested in discussing pizza toppings? Could this motivate her to bake a pizza herself? Or to call her friends for an evening out?

The CARESSES Ontology encodes all these guidelines, with the aim of offering a specific tool for endowing robots with cultural competence. In particular, this Ontology may be used to:

- *provide suitable Goals, Operators, Actions and Parameters to the planner*
- *handle the verbal interaction between the robot and the user, in a cultural competent way*
- *store user-specific information, that makes the robot attune its behaviour towards the assisted person's preferences and needs.*

Please refer to the following for additional information:

- [CARESSES project website](#)
- Bruno, B., Menicatti, R., Recchiuto, C. T., Lagrue, E., Pandey, A. K., & Sgorbissa, A. (2018, June). [Culturally-Competent Human-Robot Verbal Interaction](#) . In 2018 15th International Conference on Ubiquitous Robots (UR) (pp. 388-395). IEEE.
- Sgorbissa, A., Papadopoulos, I., Bruno, B., Koulouglioti, C., & Recchiuto, C. (2018, October). [Encoding guidelines for a culturally competent robot for elderly care](#) . In 2018 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS) (pp. 1988-1995). IEEE.
- Bruno, B., Recchiuto, C. T., Papadopoulos, I., Saffiotti, A., Koulouglioti, C., Menicatti, R., ... & Sgorbissa, A. (2019). [Knowledge Representation for Culturally Competent Personal Robots: Requirements, Design Principles, Implementation, and Assessment](#) . International Journal of Social Robotics, 1-24.

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An Ontology for culturally competent robots assisting older adults

If you want to acquire a deeper knowledge about how the CARESSES ontology can be used, we suggest to refer to the aforementioned scientific articles (Bruno et al., 2018; Sgorbissa et al., 2019; Bruno, Recchiuto et al, 2019). Additionally, if you want to see concrete examples to learn how the CARESSES Ontology is used in CARESSES, please feel free to contact us at the address info@caressesrobot.org to receive a Manual, Tutorials with exercises, video tutorials, as well as examples of TBoxes and ABoxes.

The Figure below summarizes the relationship between the TBox and the ABox in the CARESSES approach.

The Figure describes four core elements:

- Culture-generic knowledge, a layer that stores the terminology (TBox - I) required to represent all the information related to the context, the robot, and the grounding of the core values, ideally for all the cultures of the world;
- Culture-specific settings, a layer that stores the assertions (CS-ABox - II) required to represent cultural information at national level;
- Person-specific settings, a layer that stores the assertions (PS-ABox - III) required to represent the unique cultural identity, preferences and environment of the assisted person;
- Assessment & Adaptation, an algorithm (A&A) for the discovery of person-specific settings in light of culture-specific settings, e.g., relying on “educated guesses” to be confirmed through dialogue or autonomous robot observation.

In other words, Classes represents information that are *culture-agnostic*, i.e. general concepts that applies to different cultures, while Instances are used to encode cultural information both at a general (national) level and at a user-specific level.

Please refer to the aforementioned references for a detailed description of the CARESSES Ontology and how it may be used in the context of Culturally Competent Robotics. Few additional remarks will be here given:

- All Classes in the Ontology are derived from a Superclass named Topic: in our vision, everything may be (in principle) a possible conversation topic for the robot, which allows the robot to learn person-specific knowledge through dialogue and educated guesses;
- The presented Ontology should be seen as a sort of *Upper Ontology* for representing the knowledge required by a culturally competent robot. Indeed, it has been conceived

with a modular structures, where domain-specific ontologies may be integrated for extending the robot knowledge.

Examples

The following examples show possible applications of the proposed Ontology, that have been actually implemented in the CARESSES system for human-robot interaction.

Here, the relationships between Classes related to the robot's actions are shown. As mentioned before, actions' parameters may play a key role in the context of Culturally Competent Robotics, as well as goals that the robot may proactively suggest to the user.

But how may cultural information encoded? The Figure below show a portion of the ABox describing British culture-specific (GB prefix) breakfast habits.

Please notice that the [hasLikeliness](#) DataProperty is used to encode the a priori probability that an assertion in the ABox holds for a person, given that we know that she belongs to that culture (e.g. the probability that an English person has ham for breakfast), while the [hasSentence](#) DataProperties encode all sentences that the robot may pronounce while talking with the user.

In the Figure, boxes denote instances of classes (e.g., GB_GEN, GB_EATING_BREAKFAST), yellow dashed lines denote assertions of object properties (e.g., GB_BISCUITS_EATING_BREAKFAST is a filler of GB_EATING_BREAKFAST for the property [hasFood](#)). Data properties (e.g., [has Sentence](#)) appear within the box of the instance they refer to, while [hasLikeliness](#) values appear on the top-left corner of the instance they refer to and are denoted with literals instead of numbers, with 0.05 mapped to Very Low (VL), 0.1 to Low (L), 0.2 to Medium (M), 0.4 to High (H), 0.7 to Very High (VH).

Finally, let's analyze how user-specific information are encoded.

Here, again boxes denote instances of classes, but these instances represent information directly related to the user (Dorothy Smith). In particular, the [hasLikeliness](#) property corresponds to the evidence of the assertion collected through interaction with the user.

These instances, belonging to the Person-Specific ABox layer, are fillers of the corresponding instances in the Culture-Specific ABox layer for the [hasSpecific](#) property, and they may be either manually inserted in the Ontology or created in run-time acquiring information from the user (for example through verbal interaction).

Finally, notice that the black likeliness values refer to the culture-specific layer, whereas the red values refer to the person-specific layer: English people might have a Medium probability of keeping a vase in the cupboard, but we know for sure that Dorothy Smith has one, since this piece of information was added during the setup phase, or because the robot asked that question to Dorothy and she replied in the affirmative.

Classes

[Action](#) [Actor](#) [Addressing](#) [AmusementPlace](#) [Appliance](#) [ArtObject](#) [Atheism](#)
[BeliefSystem](#) [Birthday](#) [Book](#) [CallMode](#) [CelebratingEvents](#) [Childhood](#)
[CircleOfFriend](#) [Clothing](#) [Country](#) [DailyRoutine](#) [Dance](#) [DayOfTheWeek](#)
[DeathOfAClosePerson](#) [Decoration](#) [Drink](#) [EatingPlace](#) [Education](#) [Event](#)
[Family](#) [FeelingBad](#) [FeelingWell](#) [Food](#) [FoodAndDrink](#) [FoodNorm](#)
[Frequency](#) [Friend](#) [Furniture](#) [Game](#) [Goal](#) [Habit](#) [HavingHealthProblems](#)
[Heritage](#) [HistoricFactOrPeriod](#) [Hobby](#) [Home](#) [Hour](#) [HouseObject](#)
[Kitchenware](#) [Language](#) [LivingPlace](#) [Location](#) [Manner](#) [MedicalStaff](#)
[Medication](#) [Message](#) [Movie](#) [Music](#) [Norm](#) [Object](#) [Operator](#) [Parameter](#)

[PeriodOfTheDay](#) [Person](#) [PersonalCareObject](#) [Pet](#)
[PhysicalAndMentalCondition](#) [PhysicalEnvironment](#) [Pitch](#) [Proxemics](#)
[PublicPerson](#) [Quality](#) [Relative](#) [RelativeLocation](#) [Religion](#)
[ReligiousCulturalEvent](#) [Robot](#) [Room](#) [Season](#) [ShoppingPlace](#) [Singer](#)
[SleepingPlace](#) [SmartDevice](#) [SocialEnvironment](#) [SocialEvent](#) [Song](#) [Speed](#)
[Sport](#) [SportsPlayer](#) [Time](#) [TimeFormat](#) [Topic](#) [TopicAboutOnesLife](#)
[TopicOneCanHavePreferenceAbout](#) [Town](#) [TVChannel](#) [User](#) [Volume](#)
[WaitingTime](#) [Work](#) [Writer](#) [YearlyEvent](#)

Action^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Action>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Actions that may be executed by the robot. Actions are associate to parameters (Volume, Pitch, Speed, Language), to the username (Name), to the Suggestions (Topic).

has super-classes

[Topic](#)^c

[hasCParameter](#)^{op} **some** [Parameter](#)^c

[hasConfFile1](#)^{op} **some** [Topic](#)^c

[hasConfFile2](#)^{op} **some** [Topic](#)^c

[hasDistance](#)^{op} **some** [Proxemics](#)^c

[hasLanguage](#)^{op} **some** [Language](#)^c

[hasPitch](#)^{op} **some** [Pitch](#)^c

[hasSpeed](#)^{op} **some** [Speed](#)^c

[hasSuggestion](#)^{op} **some** [Topic](#)^c

[hasUserName](#)^{op} **some** [Addressing](#)^c

[hasWaitingTime](#)^{op} **some** [WaitingTime](#)^c

[hasConfFile1Name](#)^{dp} **exactly** 1

[hasConfFile2Name](#)^{dp} **exactly** 1

[hasConfirmation](#)^{dp} **exactly** 1

is in domain of

[hasCParameter](#)^{op}, [hasConfFile1](#)^{op}, [hasConfFile1Name](#)^{dp}, [hasConfFile2](#)^{op},

[hasConfFile2Name](#)^{dp}, [hasConfirmation](#)^{dp}, [hasDistance](#)^{op}, [hasLanguage](#)^{op},

[hasPitch](#)^{op}, [hasSpeed](#)^{op}, [hasSuggestion](#)^{op}, [hasUserName](#)^{op}, [hasWaitingTime](#)^{op}

is in range of

[hasAction](#)^{op}

Actor^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Actor>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes[PublicPerson](#)^c[TopicOneCanHavePreferenceAbout](#)^c**is in range of**[hasActor](#)^{op}**Addressing**^c[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Addressing>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Possible ways to address the user. In the context of the verbal interaction between the robot and the user, this conversation topic will be probably selected among the firsts (this is implemented by the ObjectProperty [hasTriggeringCondition](#)). Examples of subclasses may be: [FirstName](#), [MrLastName](#), [MrsLastName](#), [Nickname](#), ...

The DataProperty [hasNameforPlanner](#) describes how the robot should actually address the person, and its value is usually encoded in a User-Specific Individual (E.g. for the class [FirstName](#), the DataProperty [hasNameforPlanner](#) will include the actual first name of the user)

has super-classes[Topic](#)^c[hasCondition](#)^{op} **exactly 1** [Event](#)^c[hasNameforPlanner](#)^{dp} **some** string**is in range of**[hasAddressing](#)^{op}, [hasUserName](#)^{op}**AmusementPlace**^c[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#AmusementPlace>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-classes**[PhysicalEnvironment](#)^c[hasLocation](#)^{op} **some** [Location](#)^c**is disjoint with**[EatingPlace](#)^c, [LivingPlace](#)^c, [ShoppingPlace](#)^c, [SleepingPlace](#)^c**Appliance**^c[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Appliance>

is defined by<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-classes**[HouseObject^c](#)**is disjoint with**[Decoration^c](#), [Furniture^c](#), [Kitchenware^c](#)**ArtObject^c**[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#ArtObject>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

An abstract or physical object considered to fulfill a primarily independent aesthetic function.

has super-classes[Object^c](#)**has sub-classes**[Book^c](#), [Dance^c](#), [Movie^c](#), [Music^c](#), [Song^c](#)**Atheism^c**[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Atheism>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Lack of belief in gods and religions

has super-classes[BeliefSystem^c](#)**BeliefSystem^c**[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#BeliefSystem>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Ideology or set of principles. It is mainly intended in the form of religion.

Individuals of this class may be related to Individuals of the class ReligiousCulturalEvent; thus, known the user's religion, the robot would probably talk about related religious festivities.

has super-classes

[Topic^C](#)[hasEvent^{OP}](#) **some** [Event^C](#)**has sub-classes**[Atheism^C](#), [Religion^C](#)**is in range of**[hasBeliefAndValue^{OP}](#)[Birthday^C](#)[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Birthday>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-classes**[YearlyEvent^C](#)[Book^C](#)[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Book>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-classes**[ArtObject^C](#)[TopicOneCanHavePreferenceAbout^C](#)[hasPerson^{OP}](#) **some** [Writer^C](#)[CallMode^C](#)[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#CallMode>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Parameter for the VideoCall action (Audio or Video call)

has super-classes[Parameter^C](#)[CelebratingEvents^C](#)[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#CelebratingEvents>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

The habit of celebrating events (holidays, festivities, ...)

has super-classes

[Habit^C](#)

[hasEvent^{op}](#) **some** [Event^C](#)

Childhood^C

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Childhood>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[TopicAboutOnesLife^C](#)

[hasEvent^{op}](#) **some** [Event^C](#)

[hasHabit^{op}](#) **some** [Habit^C](#)

[hasPet^{op}](#) **some** [Pet^C](#)

CircleOfFriend^C

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#CircleOfFriend>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[SocialEnvironment^C](#)

[hasPerson^{op}](#) **some** [Friend^C](#)

Clothing^C

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Clothing>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[Object^C](#)

is in range of

[hasCloth^{op}](#)

Country^C

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Country>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

A nation with its own government

has super-classes

[Location](#)^c

[hasTown](#)^{op} **some** [Town](#)^c

is in range of

[hasCountry](#)^{op}

DailyRoutine^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#DailyRoutine>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Action or sequence of actions that are daily executed by the user. Possible Subclasses are: DoingPhysicalExercises, GettingDressed, HavingMeal, TakingMedicine, TakingCareOfOneself, and many others

has super-classes

[Habit](#)^c

[hasTime](#)^{op} **some** [PeriodOfTheDay](#)^c

Dance^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Dance>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[ArtObject](#)^c

[TopicOneCanHavePreferenceAbout](#)^c

DayOfTheWeek^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#DayOfTheWeek>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[Time](#)^c

DeathOfAClosePerson^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#DeathOfAClosePerson>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[Event^c](#)

Decoration^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Decoration>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[HouseObject^c](#)

is disjoint with

[Appliance^c](#), [Furniture^c](#), [Kitchenware^c](#)

Drink^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Drink>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[FoodAndDrink^c](#)

[TopicOneCanHavePreferenceAbout^c](#)

EatingPlace^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#EatingPlace>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[PhysicalEnvironment^c](#)

is disjoint with

[AmusementPlace^c](#), [LivingPlace^c](#), [ShoppingPlace^c](#), [SleepingPlace^c](#)

Education^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Education>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[TopicAboutOnesLife^c](#)**Event^c**[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Event>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

A thing that has happened, or that takes place with regularity, independently from the user's activity

has super-classes[Topic^c](#)**has sub-classes**[DeathOfAClosePerson^c](#), [HistoricFactOrPeriod^c](#), [SocialEvent^c](#), [YearlyEvent^c](#)**is in range of**[hasEvent^{op}](#)**Family^c**[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Family>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-classes**[SocialEnvironment^c](#)[hasRelatLocation^{op}](#) **some** [RelativeLocation^c](#)[hasRelative^{op}](#) **some** [Relative^c](#)**is in range of**[hasFamily^{op}](#)**is disjoint with**[Friend^c](#), [Relative^c](#)**FeelingBad^c**[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#FeelingBad>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Possible Subclasses are FeelingAfraid, FeelingAngry, FeelingLonely, FeelingWorried, ...

has super-classes[PhysicalAndMentalCondition^c](#)

FeelingWell^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#FeelingWell>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Possible Subclasses are FeelingExcited, FeelingHappy, FeelingRelaxed, FeelingStrong, ...

has super-classes

[PhysicalAndMentalCondition^c](#)

Food^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Food>

has super-classes

[FoodAndDrink^c](#)

[TopicOneCanHavePreferenceAbout^c](#)

is in range of

[hasFood^{op}](#)

FoodAndDrink^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#FoodAndDrink>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[Object^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Drink^c](#), [Food^c](#)

FoodNorm^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#FoodNorm>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Dietary restrictions, that may be related to religious or ethical aspects. Possible Subclasses are EatingHalal, EatingKosher, EatingVegetarian, ...

has super-classes

[Norm^c](#)

Frequency^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Frequency>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[Time^c](#)

is in range of

[hasFrequency^{op}](#)

Friend^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Friend>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[Person^c](#)

is disjoint with

[Family^c](#), [Relative^c](#)

Furniture^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Furniture>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[HouseObject^c](#)

[hasIn^{op}](#) **some** [Object^c](#)

[hasCoordinates^{dp}](#) **exactly** 1

is disjoint with

[Appliance^c](#), [Decoration^c](#), [Kitchenware^c](#)

Game^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Game>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[Object^c](#)

is in range of

[hasGame^{op}](#)[Goal^c](#)[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Goal>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

The DataProperty hasPDDL encode the related string, in PDDL formalism, that should be sent to the planner when the goal is required

has super-classes[Parameter^c](#)[hasPDDL^{dp}](#) **exactly** 1[hasQuestion-t^{dp}](#) **exactly** 1[hasTablet-view^{dp}](#) **exactly** 1**is in domain of**[hasPDDL^{dp}](#), [hasQuestion-t^{dp}](#), [hasTablet-view^{dp}](#)**is in range of**[hasGoal^{op}](#)[Habit^c](#)[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Habit>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Activities, routines or behaviors that are regularly repeated by the user.

Individuals of this class may be filled with Individuals to the class Time for the ObjectProperty hasCondition (conversation topics may be triggered in some specific period of the day) or hasTime (the robot may investigate if habits take place in specific times of the day).

has super-classes[Topic^c](#)[hasCondition^{op}](#) **some** [Time^c](#)[hasTime^{op}](#) **some** [Time^c](#)**has sub-classes**[CelebratingEvents^c](#), [DailyRoutine^c](#), [Hobby^c](#)**is in range of**[hasHabit^{op}](#)[HavingHealthProblems^c](#)[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#HavingHealthProblems>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

The condition of having health problems can be related to medicines taken by the user

has super-classes

[PhysicalAndMentalCondition^c](#)

[hasMedicine^{op}](#) **some** [Medication^c](#)

is in range of

[hasHealth^{op}](#), [hasHealthProblem^{op}](#)

Heritage^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Heritage>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[TopicAboutOnesLife^c](#)

HistoricFactOrPeriod^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#HistoricFactOrPeriod>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Relevant facts in the areas of politics, military, science, music, sports, arts, entertainment, ...

has super-classes

[Event^c](#)

Hobby^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Hobby>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Activities done regularly in one's leisure time for pleasure. They may be chosen accordingly to the specific targets (i.e. older adults). Examples of SubClasses may be ReadingABook, WatchingAMovie, DoingSomeCooking, GoingToAClub, MakingHennaTattoos, ...

has super-classes

[Habit](#)^c
[hasNecessaryCondition](#)^{op} **some** [Quality](#)^c
[hasTime](#)^{op} **some** [PeriodOfTheDay](#)^c

Home^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Home>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

The building where one lives. Examples of SubClasses are Apartment, CareHome (for the specific case of older adults to which the CARESSES Ontology is addressed)

has super-classes

[Location](#)^c

[hasIn](#)^{op} **some** [Room](#)^c

is in range of

[hasHome](#)^{op}

Hour^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Hour>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[Time](#)^c

HouseObject^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#HouseObject>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[Object](#)^c

[hasCoordinates](#)^{dp} **exactly** 1

[hasPrep-object](#)^{dp} **exactly** 1

has sub-classes

[Appliance](#)^c, [Decoration](#)^c, [Furniture](#)^c, [Kitchenware](#)^c, [PersonalCareObject](#)^c,
[SmartDevice](#)^c

is in domain of

[hasCoordinates](#)^{dp}, [hasPrep-object](#)^{dp}

Kitchenware^C

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Kitchenware>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[HouseObject^C](#)

is disjoint with

[Appliance^C](#), [Decoration^C](#), [Furniture^C](#)

Language^C

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Language>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Parameter related to the language in which the sentences are written

has super-classes

[Parameter^C](#)

is in range of

[hasLanguage^{op}](#)

LivingPlace^C

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#LivingPlace>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[PhysicalEnvironment^C](#)

[hasCountry^{op}](#) **some** [Country^C](#)

[hasHome^{op}](#) **some** [Home^C](#)

[hasTown^{op}](#) **some** [Town^C](#)

is disjoint with

[AmusementPlace^C](#), [EatingPlace^C](#), [ShoppingPlace^C](#), [SleepingPlace^C](#)

Location^C

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Location>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

A physical space or region, defined by geographical coordinates (absolute location) or expressed in relative terms (relative location).

has super-classes

[Topic^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Country^c](#), [Home^c](#), [PhysicalEnvironment^c](#), [RelativeLocation^c](#), [Room^c](#), [Town^c](#)

is in range of

[hasLocation^{op}](#)

Manner^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Manner>

Definitions of polite or acceptable social behaviours. They may be chosen accordingly to the specific targets (i.e. older adults) and cultural identities. Examples of SubClasses are GivingPresentsToRelativeOrFriend, StackingDishesAfterMeal, ...

has super-classes

[Norm^c](#)

is in range of

[hasManner^{op}](#)

MedicalStaff^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#MedicalStaff>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[Person^c](#)

Medication^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Medication>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[Object^c](#)

is in range of

[hasMedicine^{op}](#)

Message^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Message>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Messages encoded for the SendMsgAction

has super-classes

[Parameter](#)^C

[hasCompulsory-recipient](#)^{dp} **exactly** 1

[hasMessage](#)^{dp} **exactly** 1

is in domain of

[hasCompulsory-recipient](#)^{dp}, [hasMessage](#)^{dp}

Movie^C

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Movie>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[ArtObject](#)^C

[TopicOneCanHavePreferenceAbout](#)^C

[hasActor](#)^{op} **some** [Actor](#)^C

Music^C

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Music>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[ArtObject](#)^C

[TopicOneCanHavePreferenceAbout](#)^C

[hasPerson](#)^{op} **some** [Singer](#)^C

[hasSong](#)^{op} **some** [Song](#)^C

is in range of

[hasMusic](#)^{op}

Norm^C

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Norm>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Guidelines about what is considered correct or incorrect speaking of social behavior in a particular group, social unit or cultural identities.

has super-classes

[Topic^c](#)

has sub-classes

[FoodNorm^c](#), [Manner^c](#)

is in range of

[hasNorm^{op}](#)

Object^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Object>

Abstracts objects, with no physical referents and that does not exist at any particular time or place, and concrete objects

has super-classes

[Topic^c](#)

has sub-classes

[ArtObject^c](#), [Clothing^c](#), [FoodAndDrink^c](#), [Game^c](#), [HouseObject^c](#), [Medication^c](#), [Pet^c](#),
[Robot^c](#), [Sport^c](#), [TVChannel^c](#)

Operator^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Operator>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

This class includes all Operators that should be sent to the planner for the execution of actions. Operators achieve Goals by implementing Actions

has super-classes

[Topic^c](#)

[hasAction^{op}](#) **some** [Action^c](#)

[hasGoal^{op}](#) **exactly** 1 [Goal^c](#)

[hasUDDL^{dp}](#) **exactly** 1

is in domain of

[hasAction^{op}](#), [hasUDDL^{dp}](#)

Parameter^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Parameter>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Parameters associated to actions

has super-classes

[Topic^c](#)

has sub-classes

[CallMode^c](#), [Goal^c](#), [Language^c](#), [Message^c](#), [Pitch^c](#), [Proxemics^c](#), [Speed^c](#), [TimeFormat^c](#),
[Volume^c](#), [WaitingTime^c](#)

PeriodOfTheDay^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#PeriodOfTheDay>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[Time^c](#)

Person^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Person>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Persons in the social, physical and cultural environemnt of the user

has super-classes

[Topic^c](#)

[hasEmail^{dp}](#) **exactly** 1

[hasLine^{dp}](#) **exactly** 1

[hasPhone^{dp}](#) **exactly** 1

[hasSkype^{dp}](#) **exactly** 1

[hasTelegram^{dp}](#) **exactly** 1

has sub-classes

[Friend^c](#), [MedicalStaff^c](#), [PublicPerson^c](#), [Relative^c](#)

is in domain of

[hasEmail^{dp}](#), [hasLine^{dp}](#), [hasPhone^{dp}](#), [hasSkype^{dp}](#), [hasTelegram^{dp}](#)

is in range of

[hasPerson^{op}](#)

PersonalCareObject^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#PersonalCareObject>

is defined by<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-classes**[HouseObject^c](#)**Pet^c**back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Pet>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-classes**[Object^c](#)[TopicOneCanHavePreferenceAbout^c](#)**is in range of**[hasPet^{op}](#)**PhysicalAndMentalCondition^c**back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#PhysicalAndMentalCondition>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

The condition or state of the body or mind

has super-classes[Topic^c](#)**has sub-classes**[FeelingBad^c](#), [FeelingWell^c](#), [HavingHealthProblems^c](#)**is in range of**[hasFeeling^{op}](#), [hasPhysicalAndMentalState^{op}](#)**PhysicalEnvironment^c**back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#PhysicalEnvironment>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

All tangible space regions that support and influence the user's life

has super-classes[Location^c](#)**has sub-classes**[AmusementPlace^c](#), [EatingPlace^c](#), [LivingPlace^c](#), [ShoppingPlace^c](#), [SleepingPlace^c](#)

is in range of

[hasPhysicalEnvironment^{op}](#)

Pitch^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Pitch>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Voice pitch for all actions involving verbal interaction

has super-classes

[Parameter^c](#)

is in range of

[hasPitch^{op}](#)

Proxemics^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Proxemics>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Distance parameter for the ApproachUser action

has super-classes

[Parameter^c](#)

is in range of

[hasDistance^{op}](#)

PublicPerson^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#PublicPerson>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[Person^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Actor^c](#), [Singer^c](#), [SportsPlayer^c](#), [Writer^c](#)

Quality^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Quality>

is defined by<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Basic entities to perceive or measure: shapes, colors, sizes, sounds, smells,...

has super-classes[Topic^c](#)**is in range of**[hasQuality^{op}](#)**Relative^c**[back to ToC or Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Relative>

is defined by<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-classes**[Person^c](#)**is in range of**[hasRelative^{op}](#)**is disjoint with**[Family^c](#), [Friend^c](#)**RelativeLocation^c**[back to ToC or Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#RelativeLocation>

is defined by<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

The position of something expressed in relative terms (e.g. Close, Far, VeryFar, ...)

has super-classes[Location^c](#)**is in range of**[hasRelatLocation^{op}](#)**Religion^c**[back to ToC or Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Religion>

is defined by<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Individuals of this class may be filled with Individuals of the class FoodNorm for the ObjectProperty hasNorm; thus, known the user's religion, the robot would probably investigate aspects related to possible alimentary restrictions

Individuals of this class may be filled with Individuals of the class ReligiousCulturalEvent for the ObjectProperty hasEvent; thus, known the user's religion, the robot would probably talk about related religious festivities.

has super-classes

[BeliefSystem](#)^C

[hasEvent](#)^{OP} **some** [ReligiousCulturalEvent](#)^C

[hasNorm](#)^{OP} **some** [FoodNorm](#)^C

is in range of

[hasReligion](#)^{OP}

ReligiousCulturalEvent^C

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#ReligiousCulturalEvent>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Any event related to religious celebrations

has super-classes

[YearlyEvent](#)^C

Robot^C

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Robot>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

The user's robot . An instance of the class Robot may be connected with instances of the class Goal, in order to encode all goals that may be achieved by the robot

has super-classes

[Object](#)^C

[hasGoal](#)^{OP} **some** [Goal](#)^C

is in range of

[hasRobot](#)^{OP}

Room^C

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Room>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[Location](#)^C

[hasAdjacent](#)^{op} **some** [Room](#)^c

[hasIn](#)^{op} **some** [HouseObject](#)^c

[hasIn](#)^{op} **some** [Object](#)^c

is in range of

[hasRoom](#)^{op}

Season^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Season>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[Time](#)^c

ShoppingPlace^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#ShoppingPlace>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[PhysicalEnvironment](#)^c

[hasLocation](#)^{op} **some** [Location](#)^c

is disjoint with

[AmusementPlace](#)^c, [EatingPlace](#)^c, [LivingPlace](#)^c, [SleepingPlace](#)^c

Singer^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Singer>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[PublicPerson](#)^c

SleepingPlace^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#SleepingPlace>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[PhysicalEnvironment](#)^c

[hasRoom](#)^{op} **some** [Room](#)^c

is disjoint with

[AmusementPlace](#)^c, [EatingPlace](#)^c, [LivingPlace](#)^c, [ShoppingPlace](#)^c

SmartDevice^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#SmartDevice>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[HouseObject](#)^c

[hasAs-sensor](#)^{dp} **exactly** 1

[hasLocations](#)^{dp} **exactly** 1

[hasOperations](#)^{dp} **exactly** 1

[hasStatus](#)^{dp} **exactly** 1

[hasType](#)^{dp} **exactly** 1

is in domain of

[hasAs-sensor](#)^{dp}, [hasLocations](#)^{dp}, [hasOperations](#)^{dp}, [hasStatus](#)^{dp}, [hasType](#)^{dp}

SocialEnvironment^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#SocialEnvironment>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Social relationships that influence the user's life (friends, family, ...)

has super-classes

[Topic](#)^c

has sub-classes

[CircleOfFriend](#)^c, [Family](#)^c

is in range of

[hasSocialEnvironment](#)^{op}

SocialEvent^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#SocialEvent>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Any occasion/event that involves social interaction.

has super-classes

[Event](#)^C
[YearlyEvent](#)^C
[hasRelative](#)^{op} **some** [Relative](#)^C

Song^C

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Song>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[ArtObject](#)^C
[hasPerson](#)^{op} **some** [Singer](#)^C

is in range of

[hasSong](#)^{op}

Speed^C

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Speed>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Voice speed for all actions involving verbal interaction

has super-classes

[Parameter](#)^C

is in range of

[hasSpeed](#)^{op}

Sport^C

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Sport>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[Object](#)^C
[TopicOneCanHavePreferenceAbout](#)^C
[hasSportsPlayer](#)^{op} **some** [SportsPlayer](#)^C

SportsPlayer^C

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#SportsPlayer>

is defined by<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-classes**[PublicPerson^C](#)[TopicOneCanHavePreferenceAbout^C](#)**is in range of**[hasSportsPlayer^{op}](#)**Time^C**[back to ToC or Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Time>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-classes**[Topic^C](#)**has sub-classes**[DayOfTheWeek^C](#), [Frequency^C](#), [Hour^C](#), [PeriodOfTheDay^C](#), [Season^C](#)**is in range of**[hasTime^{op}](#)**TimeFormat^C**[back to ToC or Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#TimeFormat>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

12 hr or 24hr

has super-classes[Parameter^C](#)**Topic^C**[back to ToC or Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Topic>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Conversation topics that may be explored by the robot.

Conversation topics are defined by a set of DataProperties:

- hasLikeliness (it reflects the probability that the user will have a positive attitude towards that topic, given his cultural identity (if the instance belong to the Culture-

Specific ABox), or given the evidence collected through the interaction with the user (if the instance belong to the Person-Specific ABox).

- hasQuestion (encoded sentences used by the robot to ask the general user's feedback about the topic)
- hasQuestionContextual (encoded sentences used by the robot to ask the user's feedback related to the specific context)
- hasQuestionGoal (encoded sentences used by the robot to ask the user about activities to be performed)
- has PositiveSentence (encoded sentences used by the robot when a positive feedback is received)
- has PositiveAndWait (encoded sentences used by the robot when a positive feedback is received. With these sentences, the robot invites the user to freely talk about a conversation topic)
- hasNegativeSentence (encoded sentences used by the robot when a negative feedback is received)
- hasKeyword1 & hasKeyword2 (keywords that may trigger a conversation topic)

Culture-specific instances of subclasses of Topic may be filled with Person-specific instances for the hasSpecific ObjectProperty

has super-classes

[entity](#)^c
[hasSpecific](#)^{op} **some** [Topic](#)^c
[hasKeyword1](#)^{dp} **some** [string](#)
[hasKeyword2](#)^{dp} **some** [string](#)
[hasLikeliness](#)^{dp} **some** [decimal](#)
[hasName](#)^{dp} **some** [string](#)
[hasFull](#)^{dp} **exactly** 1
[hasValue](#)^{dp} **exactly** 1

has sub-classes

[Action](#)^c, [Addressing](#)^c, [BeliefSystem](#)^c, [Event](#)^c, [Habit](#)^c, [Location](#)^c, [Norm](#)^c, [Object](#)^c,
[Operator](#)^c, [Parameter](#)^c, [Person](#)^c, [PhysicalAndMentalCondition](#)^c, [Quality](#)^c,
[SocialEnvironment](#)^c, [Time](#)^c, [TopicAboutOnesLife](#)^c,
[TopicOneCanHavePreferenceAbout](#)^c, [User](#)^c

is in domain of

[has h correlation](#)^{op}, [has m correlation](#)^{op}, [has v h correlation](#)^{op}, [has v l correlation](#)^{op},
[hasActor](#)^{op}, [hasAddressing](#)^{op}, [hasAdjacent](#)^{op}, [hasBeliefAndValue](#)^{op}, [hasCloth](#)^{op},
[hasCondition](#)^{op}, [hasCorrelation](#)^{op}, [hasCountry](#)^{op}, [hasEvent](#)^{op}, [hasFamily](#)^{op},
[hasFeeling](#)^{op}, [hasFood](#)^{op}, [hasFrequency](#)^{op}, [hasFull](#)^{dp}, [hasGame](#)^{op}, [hasGoal](#)^{op},
[hasHabit](#)^{op}, [hasHealth](#)^{op}, [hasHealthProblem](#)^{op}, [hasHome](#)^{op}, [hasIn](#)^{op},
[hasKeyword1](#)^{dp}, [hasKeyword2](#)^{dp}, [hasLife](#)^{op}, [hasLikeliness](#)^{dp}, [hasLocation](#)^{op},
[hasManner](#)^{op}, [hasMedicine](#)^{op}, [hasMusic](#)^{op}, [hasName](#)^{dp}, [hasNameforPlanner](#)^{dp},
[hasNecessaryCondition](#)^{op}, [hasNorm](#)^{op}, [hasObject](#)^{op}, [hasPerson](#)^{op}, [hasPet](#)^{op},
[hasPhysicalAndMentalState](#)^{op}, [hasPhysicalEnvironment](#)^{op}, [hasQuality](#)^{op},
[hasRelatLocation](#)^{op}, [hasRelative](#)^{op}, [hasReligion](#)^{op}, [hasRobot](#)^{op}, [hasRoom](#)^{op},
[hasSentence](#)^{dp}, [hasSocialEnvironment](#)^{op}, [hasSong](#)^{op}, [hasSpecific](#)^{op},
[hasSportsPlayer](#)^{op}, [hasTime](#)^{op}, [hasTopic](#)^{op}, [hasTown](#)^{op}, [hasTriggeringCondition](#)^{op},
[hasURL](#)^{dp}, [hasValue](#)^{dp}

is in range of

[has h correlation](#)^{op}, [has m correlation](#)^{op}, [has v h correlation](#)^{op}, [has v l correlation](#)^{op},
[hasAdjacent](#)^{op}, [hasCParameter](#)^{op}, [hasCondition](#)^{op}, [hasConfFile1](#)^{op}, [hasConfFile2](#)^{op},
[hasCorrelation](#)^{op}, [hasIn](#)^{op}, [hasNecessaryCondition](#)^{op}, [hasObject](#)^{op}, [hasSpecific](#)^{op},
[hasSuggestion](#)^{op}, [hasTopic](#)^{op}, [hasTriggeringCondition](#)^{op}

TopicAboutOnesLife^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#TopicAboutOnesLife>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology/>

Relevant facts for the user's past and present life (childhood, education, heritage, work, ...)

has super-classes

[Topic](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Childhood](#)^c, [Education](#)^c, [Heritage](#)^c, [Work](#)^c

is in range of

[hasLife](#)^{op}

TopicOneCanHavePreferenceAbout^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#TopicOneCanHavePreferenceAbout>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology/>

All things that may be expressed in terms of "preference" (e.g. what is your favourite ... ?)

has super-classes

[Topic](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Actor](#)^c, [Book](#)^c, [Dance](#)^c, [Drink](#)^c, [Food](#)^c, [Movie](#)^c, [Music](#)^c, [Pet](#)^c, [Sport](#)^c, [SportsPlayer](#)^c

Town^c

back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Town>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology/>

has super-classes

[Location](#)^c

[hasCountry](#)^{op} **exactly** 1 [Country](#)^c

is in range of

[hasTown^{op}](#)

TVChannel^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#TVChannel>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[Object^c](#)

[hasUrl-article^{dp}](#) **exactly** 1

[hasUrl-root^{dp}](#) **exactly** 1

is in domain of

[hasUrl-article^{dp}](#), [hasUrl-root^{dp}](#)

User^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#User>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Person to which the user-specific information of the Ontology refers

has super-classes

[Topic^c](#)

[hasAddressing^{op}](#) **some** [Addressing^c](#)

[hasBeliefAndValue^{op}](#) **some** [BeliefSystem^c](#)

[hasCloth^{op}](#) **some** [Clothing^c](#)

[hasEvent^{op}](#) **some** [Event^c](#)

[hasFeeling^{op}](#) **some** [FeelingBad^c](#)

[hasFeeling^{op}](#) **some** [FeelingWell^c](#)

[hasFood^{op}](#) **some** [Food^c](#)

[hasGame^{op}](#) **some** [Game^c](#)

[hasHabit^{op}](#) **some** [Habit^c](#)

[hasHealth^{op}](#) **some** [PhysicalAndMentalCondition^c](#)

[hasHealthProblem^{op}](#) **some** [HavingHealthProblems^c](#)

[hasLife^{op}](#) **some** [TopicAboutOnesLife^c](#)

[hasManner^{op}](#) **some** [Manner^c](#)

[hasMusic^{op}](#) **some** [Music^c](#)

[hasNorm^{op}](#) **some** [Norm^c](#)

[hasObject^{op}](#) **some** [Object^c](#)

[hasObject^{op}](#) **some** [TopicOneCanHavePreferenceAbout^c](#)

[hasPhysicalAndMentalState^{op}](#) **some** [PhysicalAndMentalCondition^c](#)

[hasPhysicalEnvironment](#)^{op} **some** [PhysicalEnvironment](#)^c
[hasReligion](#)^{op} **some** [Religion](#)^c
[hasRobot](#)^{op} **some** [Robot](#)^c
[hasSocialEnvironment](#)^{op} **some** [SocialEnvironment](#)^c

Volume^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Volume>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Voice volume for all actions involving verbal interaction

has super-classes

[Parameter](#)^c

WaitingTime^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#WaitingTime>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Waiting Time parameter for the AcceptRequest Action

has super-classes

[Parameter](#)^c

is in range of

[hasWaitingTime](#)^{op}

Work^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Work>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes

[TopicAboutOnesLife](#)^c

Writer^c

[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#Writer>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-classes[PublicPerson^c](#)**YearlyEvent^c**[back to ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#YearlyEvent>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Any event that takes place regularly every year

has super-classes[Event^c](#)**has sub-classes**[Birthday^c](#), [ReligiousCulturalEvent^c](#), [SocialEvent^c](#)

Object Properties

[has h correlation](#) [has m correlation](#) [has v h correlation](#) [has v l correlation](#)
[hasAction](#) [hasActor](#) [hasAddressing](#) [hasAdjacent](#) [hasBeliefAndValue](#)
[hasCloth](#) [hasCondition](#) [hasConfFile1](#) [hasConfFile2](#) [hasCorrelation](#)
[hasCountry](#) [hasCParameter](#) [hasDistance](#) [hasEvent](#) [hasFamily](#) [hasFeeling](#)
[hasFood](#) [hasFrequency](#) [hasGame](#) [hasGoal](#) [hasHabit](#) [hasHealth](#)
[hasHealthProblem](#) [hasHome](#) [hasIn](#) [hasLanguage](#) [hasLife](#) [hasLocation](#)
[hasManner](#) [hasMedicine](#) [hasMusic](#) [hasNecessaryCondition](#) [hasNorm](#)
[hasObject](#) [hasPerson](#) [hasPet](#) [hasPhysicalAndMentalState](#)
[hasPhysicalEnvironment](#) [hasPitch](#) [hasQuality](#) [hasRelative](#) [hasRelatLocation](#)
[hasReligion](#) [hasRobot](#) [hasRoom](#) [hasSocialEnvironment](#) [hasSong](#)
[hasSpecific](#) [hasSpeed](#) [hasSportsPlayer](#) [hasSuggestion](#) [hasTime](#) [hasTopic](#)
[hasTown](#) [hasTriggeringCondition](#) [hasUserName](#) [hasWaitingTime](#)

has h correlation^{op}[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasHCorrelation>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasCorrelation^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Topic^c](#)

has m correlation^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasMCorrelation>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-properties

[hasCorrelation^{op}](#)

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

has range

[Topic^c](#)

has v h correlation^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasVHCorrelation>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-properties

[hasCorrelation^{op}](#)

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

has range

[Topic^c](#)

has v l correlation^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasVLCorrelation>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-properties

[hasCorrelation^{op}](#)

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

has range

[Topic^c](#)

hasAction^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasAction>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

A relation that holds between Operators and Actions

has super-properties

[top object property^{op}](#)

has domain

[Operator^c](#)

has range

[Action^c](#)

hasActor^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasActor>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-properties

[hasPerson^{op}](#)

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

has range

[Actor^c](#)

hasAddressing^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasAddressing>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

ObjectProperty used for let the robot talk about possible ways to address the user

has super-properties

[hasTopic^{op}](#)

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

has range

[Addressing^c](#)

hasAdjacent^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasAdjacent>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Relationship of closeness between Objects and/or Locations

has super-properties

[top object property](#)^{op}

has sub-properties

[hasIn](#)^{op}

has domain

[Topic](#)^c

has range

[Topic](#)^c

[hasBeliefAndValue](#)^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasBeliefAndValue>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

ObjectProperty used for let the robot talk about user's beliefs and values

has super-properties

[hasTopic](#)^{op}

has sub-properties

[hasReligion](#)^{op}

has domain

[Topic](#)^c

has range

[BeliefSystem](#)^c

[hasCloth](#)^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasCloth>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

ObjectProperty used for let the robot talk about the user's clothes

has super-properties

[hasObject](#)^{op}

[hasTopic](#)^{op}

has domain

[Topic](#)^c

has range

[Clothing](#)^c

hasCondition^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasCondition>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-properties

[top object property^{op}](#)

has sub-properties

[hasNecessaryCondition^{op}](#), [hasTriggeringCondition^{op}](#)

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

has range

[Topic^c](#)

hasConfFile1^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasConfFile1>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

The individual filler of this property is used for building the configuration files for the related action

has super-properties

[top object property^{op}](#)

has domain

[Action^c](#)

has range

[Topic^c](#)

hasConfFile2^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasConfFile2>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

The individual filler of this property is used for building the configuration files for the related action

has super-properties

[top object property^{op}](#)

has domain

[Action^c](#)

has range[Topic^c](#)**hasCorrelation^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)**IRI:** <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasCorrelation>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Correlations between Individuals, even belonging to different Classes. An HCorrelation implies that, if a UserSpecific instances with an high DataProperty HasLikeliness value is added, the hasLiklelines of the other individuals should be increased. A VLCorrelation impliease that if a UserSpecific instances with an high DataProperty HasLikeliness value is added, the hasLiklelines of the other individuals should be decreased.

has super-properties[top object property^{op}](#)**has sub-properties**[has h correlation^{op}](#), [has m correlation^{op}](#), [has v h correlation^{op}](#), [has v l correlation^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Topic^c](#)**hasCountry^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)**IRI:** <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasCountry>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasLocation^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Country^c](#)**hasCParameter^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)**IRI:** <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasCParameter>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Cultural Parameters to be associated to Actions

has super-properties[top object property^{op}](#)**has sub-properties**[hasDistance^{op}](#), [hasLanguage^{op}](#), [hasPitch^{op}](#), [hasSpeed^{op}](#), [hasSuggestion^{op}](#),
[hasUserName^{op}](#), [hasWaitingTime^{op}](#)**has domain**[Action^c](#)**has range**[Topic^c](#)**hasDistance^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasDistance>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasCParameter^{op}](#)**has domain**[Action^c](#)**has range**[Proxemics^c](#)**hasEvent^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasEvent>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

ObjectProperty used for let the robot talk about events relevant for the user's life

has super-properties[hasTopic^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Event^c](#)**hasFamily^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasFamily>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-properties[hasSocialEnvironment](#)^{op}**has domain**[Topic](#)^c**has range**[Family](#)^c**hasFeeling**^{op}[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasFeeling>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasPhysicalAndMentalState](#)^{op}**has domain**[Topic](#)^c**has range**[PhysicalAndMentalCondition](#)^c**hasFood**^{op}[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasFood>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

ObjectProperty used for let the robot talk about food

has super-properties[hasObject](#)^{op}[hasTopic](#)^{op}**has domain**[Topic](#)^c**has range**[Food](#)^c**hasFrequency**^{op}[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasFrequency>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasTime](#)^{op}

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

has range

[Frequency^c](#)

hasGame^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasGame>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

ObjectProperty used for let the robot talk about games

has super-properties

[hasObject^{op}](#)

[hasTopic^{op}](#)

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

has range

[Game^c](#)

hasGoal^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasGoal>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

ObjectProperty used for let the robot talk about possible activities

has super-properties

[hasTopic^{op}](#)

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

has range

[Goal^c](#)

hasHabit^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasHabit>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

ObjectProperty used for let the robot talk about user's regular / periodical activities

has super-properties[hasTopic^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Habit^c](#)**hasHealth^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasHealth>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

ObjectProperty used for let the robot talk about the user's health

has super-properties[hasTopic^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[HavingHealthProblems^c](#)**hasHealthProblem^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasHealthProblem>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasPhysicalAndMentalState^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[HavingHealthProblems^c](#)**hasHome^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasHome>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasLocation^{op}](#)**has domain**

[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Home^c](#)[hasIn^{op}](#)[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasIn>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Inclusion relationship between Objects and/or Location

has super-properties[hasAdjacent^{op}](#)[hasTopic^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Topic^c](#)[hasLanguage^{op}](#)[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasLanguage>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasCParameter^{op}](#)**has domain**[Action^c](#)**has range**[Language^c](#)[hasLife^{op}](#)[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasLife>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

ObjectProperty used for let the robot talk about the user's life

has super-properties[hasTopic^{op}](#)**has domain**

[Topic^c](#)**has range**[TopicAboutOnesLife^c](#)**hasLocation^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasLocation>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

ObjectProperty used for let the robot talk about places that are relevant for the user

has super-properties[hasTopic^{op}](#)**has sub-properties**[hasCountry^{op}](#), [hasHome^{op}](#), [hasRelatLocation^{op}](#), [hasRoom^{op}](#), [hasTown^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Location^c](#)**hasManner^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasManner>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

ObjectProperty used for let the robot talk about good manners

has super-properties[hasTopic^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Manner^c](#)**hasMedicine^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasMedicine>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

ObjectProperty used for let the robot talk about medicines relevant for the user

has super-properties[hasObject^{op}](#)[hasTopic^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Medication^c](#)**hasMusic^{op}**[back to ToC or Object Property ToC](#)**IRI:** <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasMusic>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasObject^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Music^c](#)**hasNecessaryCondition^{op}**[back to ToC or Object Property ToC](#)**IRI:** <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasNecessaryCondition>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Filler of this ObjectProperty is an Event or Time or Quality that allows the robot to talk about a specific topic

has super-properties[hasCondition^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Topic^c](#)**hasNorm^{op}**[back to ToC or Object Property ToC](#)**IRI:** <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasNorm>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

ObjectProperty used for let the robot talk about social norms

has super-properties[hasTopic^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Norm^c](#)**hasObject^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasObject>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Relationships between User and Objects

has super-properties[hasTopic^{op}](#)**has sub-properties**[hasCloth^{op}](#), [hasFood^{op}](#), [hasGame^{op}](#), [hasMedicine^{op}](#), [hasMusic^{op}](#), [hasPet^{op}](#),
[hasSong^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Topic^c](#)**hasPerson^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasPerson>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

ObjectProperty used for let the robot talk about persons relevant for the user's life

has super-properties[hasTopic^{op}](#)**has sub-properties**[hasActor^{op}](#), [hasRelative^{op}](#), [hasSportsPlayer^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Person^c](#)**hasPet^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasPet>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-properties

[hasObject](#)^{op}

has domain

[Topic](#)^c

has range

[Pet](#)^c

[hasPhysicalAndMentalState](#)^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasPhysicalAndMentalState>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

ObjectProperty used for let the robot talk about the physical and mental state of the user

has super-properties

[hasTopic](#)^{op}

has sub-properties

[hasFeeling](#)^{op}, [hasHealthProblem](#)^{op}

has domain

[Topic](#)^c

has range

[PhysicalAndMentalCondition](#)^c

[hasPhysicalEnvironment](#)^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasPhysicalEnvironment>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-properties

[hasTopic](#)^{op}

has domain

[Topic](#)^c

has range

[PhysicalEnvironment](#)^c

[hasPitch](#)^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasPitch>

is defined by<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasCParameter^{op}](#)**has domain**[Action^c](#)**has range**[Pitch^c](#)**hasQuality^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasQuality>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasTopic^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Quality^c](#)**hasRelative^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasRelative>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasPerson^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Relative^c](#)**hasRelatLocation^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasRelatLocation>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasLocation^{op}](#)**has domain**

[Topic^c](#)**has range**[RelativeLocation^c](#)[hasReligion^{op}](#)[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasReligion>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

ObjectProperty used for let the robot talk about user's religion

has super-properties[hasBeliefAndValue^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Religion^c](#)[hasRobot^{op}](#)[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasRobot>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasTopic^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Robot^c](#)[hasRoom^{op}](#)[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasRoom>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasLocation^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Room^c](#)

hasSocialEnvironment^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasSocialEnvironment>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-properties

[hasTopic^{op}](#)

has sub-properties

[hasFamily^{op}](#)

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

has range

[SocialEnvironment^c](#)

hasSong^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasSong>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-properties

[hasObject^{op}](#)

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

has range

[Song^c](#)

hasSpecific^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasSpecific>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Instances, belonging to the Person-Specific ABox layer, are fillers of the corresponding instances in the Culture-Specific ABox layer for the hasSpecific property,

has super-properties

[top object property^{op}](#)

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

has range

[Topic^c](#)

hasSpeed^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasSpeed>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-properties

[hasCParameter^{op}](#)

has domain

[Action^c](#)

has range

[Speed^c](#)

hasSportsPlayer^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasSportsPlayer>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-properties

[hasPerson^{op}](#)

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

has range

[SportsPlayer^c](#)

hasSuggestion^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasSuggestion>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

has super-properties

[hasCParameter^{op}](#)

has domain

[Action^c](#)

has range

[Topic^c](#)

hasTime^{op}

back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasTime>

is defined by<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasTopic^{op}](#)**has sub-properties**[hasFrequency^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Time^c](#)**hasTopic^{op}**[back to ToC or Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasTopic>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

All object properties that allow the robot to talk about conversation topics

has characteristics: transitive**has super-properties**[top object property^{op}](#)**has sub-properties**[hasAddressing^{op}](#), [hasBeliefAndValue^{op}](#), [hasCloth^{op}](#), [hasEvent^{op}](#), [hasFood^{op}](#), [hasGame^{op}](#), [hasGoal^{op}](#), [hasHabit^{op}](#), [hasHealth^{op}](#), [hasIn^{op}](#), [hasLife^{op}](#), [hasLocation^{op}](#), [hasManner^{op}](#), [hasMedicine^{op}](#), [hasNorm^{op}](#), [hasObject^{op}](#), [hasPerson^{op}](#), [hasPhysicalAndMentalState^{op}](#), [hasPhysicalEnvironment^{op}](#), [hasQuality^{op}](#), [hasRobot^{op}](#), [hasSocialEnvironment^{op}](#), [hasTime^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Topic^c](#)**hasTown^{op}**[back to ToC or Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasTown>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasLocation^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)

has range[Town^c](#)**hasTriggeringCondition^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasTriggeringCondition>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Filler of this ObjectProperty is an Event or Time or Quality that triggers a specific dialogue

has super-properties[hasCondition^{op}](#)**has domain**[Topic^c](#)**has range**[Topic^c](#)**hasUserName^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasUserName>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasCParameter^{op}](#)**has domain**[Action^c](#)**has range**[Addressing^c](#)**hasWaitingTime^{op}**[back to ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasWaitingTime>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>**has super-properties**[hasCParameter^{op}](#)**has domain**[Action^c](#)**has range**[WaitingTime^c](#)

Data Properties

[hasAs-sensor](#)
[hasCompulsory-recipient](#)
[hasConfFile1Name](#)
[hasConfFile2Name](#)
[hasConfirmation](#)
[hasCoordinates](#)
[hasEmail](#)
[hasFull](#)
[hasKeyword1](#)
[hasKeyword2](#)
[hasLikeliness](#)
[hasLine](#)
[hasLocations](#)
[hasMessage](#)
[hasName](#)
[hasNameforPlanner](#)
[hasOperations](#)
[hasPDDL](#)
[hasPhone](#)
[hasPrep-object](#)
[hasQuestion-t](#)
[hasSentence](#)
[hasSkype](#)
[hasStatus](#)
[hasTablet-view](#)
[hasTelegram](#)
[hasType](#)
[hasUDDL](#)
[hasURL](#)
[hasUrl-article](#)
[hasUrl-root](#)
[hasValue](#)

hasAs-sensor^{dp}

[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasAs-sensor>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

String for automatically composing sentences. It refers to Smart Devices

has super-properties

[top data property^{dp}](#)

has domain

[SmartDevice^c](#)

hasCompulsory-recipient^{dp}

[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasCompulsory-recipient>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Compulsory recipient for related messages.

has super-properties

[top data property^{dp}](#)

has domain

[Message^c](#)

hasConfFile1Name^{dp}

[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasConfFile1Name>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Configuration file for actions

has super-properties

top data property^{dp}

has domain

[Action](#)^c

[hasConfFile2Name](#)^{dp}

back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasConfFile2Name>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Configuration file for actions

has super-properties

top data property^{dp}

has domain

[Action](#)^c

[hasConfirmation](#)^{dp}

back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasConfirmation>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Confirmation sentence before launching a goal

has super-properties

top data property^{dp}

has domain

[Action](#)^c

[hasCoordinates](#)^{dp}

back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasCoordinates>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Coordinates of objects in the environment

has super-properties

top data property^{dp}

has domain

[HouseObject](#)^c

hasEmail^{dp}

[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasEmail>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

E-mail address of contacts

has super-properties

[top data property^{dp}](#)

has domain

[Person^c](#)

hasFull^{dp}

[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasFull>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

hasFull field for building configuration files of actions

has super-properties

[top data property^{dp}](#)

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

hasKeyword1^{dp}

[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasKeyword1>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Triggering keyword for conversation topics

has super-properties

[top data property^{dp}](#)

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

hasKeyword2^{dp}

[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasKeyword2>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Triggering keyword for conversation topics

has super-properties

top data property^{dp}

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

hasLikeliness^{dp}

[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasLikeliness>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Likeliness value for conversation topics. It corresponds to a reasonable estimate, to the best of available knowledge, of the a posteriori probability of the assertion.

- In the Culture-Specific Layer, Likeliness values are used to specify how appropriate each instance is for the each culture, and guide the robot's behaviour.
- In the Person-Specific Layer, the likeliness corresponds to the evidence of the assertion collected through interaction with the user.

has super-properties

top data property^{dp}

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

hasLine^{dp}

[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasLine>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Line account of the user's contact

has super-properties

top data property^{dp}

has domain

[Person^c](#)

hasLocations^{dp}

[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasLocations>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Location of the smart device

has super-properties

top data property^{dp}

has domain

[SmartDevice](#)^c

[hasMessage](#)^{dp}

back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasMessage>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Preloaded messages for the SendMessageAction

has super-properties

top data property^{dp}

has domain

[Message](#)^c

[hasName](#)^{dp}

back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasName>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Field used to automatically generate sentences

has super-properties

top data property^{dp}

has domain

[Topic](#)^c

[hasNameforPlanner](#)^{dp}

back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasNameforPlanner>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

String to be sent to the planner

has super-properties

top data property^{dp}

has domain[Topic^c](#)**hasOperations^{dp}**[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)**IRI:** <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasOperations>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Operations that can be executed with smart devices

has super-propertiestop data property^{dp}**has domain**[SmartDevice^c](#)**hasPDDL^{dp}**[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)**IRI:** <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasPDDL>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Planning tasks (written in the PDDL formalism) that should be sent to the planner

has super-propertiestop data property^{dp}**has domain**[Goal^c](#)**hasPhone^{dp}**[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)**IRI:** <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasPhone>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Phone number of user's contacts

has super-propertiestop data property^{dp}**has domain**[Person^c](#)**hasPrep-object^{dp}**[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasPrep-object>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Field used for automatically building sentences

has super-properties

top data property^{dp}

has domain

[HouseObject](#)^c

hasQuestion-t^{dp}

[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasQuestion-t>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Question to be shown on the tablet

has super-properties

top data property^{dp}

has domain

[Goal](#)^c

hasSentence^{dp}

[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasSentence>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Sentences that the robot may pronounce during the interaction with the user. Subproperties of hasSentence may be:

hasQuestion (encoded sentences used by the robot to ask the general user's feedback about the topic)

- hasQuestionContextual (encoded sentences used by the robot to ask the user's feedback related to the specific context)
- hasQuestionGoal (encoded sentences used by the robot to ask the user about activities to be performed)
- has PositiveSentence (encoded sentences used by the robot when a positive feedback is received)
- has PositiveAndWait (encoded sentences used by the robot when a positive feedback is received. With these sentences, the robot invites the user to freely talk about a conversation topic)
- hasNegativeSentence (encoded sentences used by the robot when a negative feedback is received)

has super-propertiestop data property^{dp}**has domain**[Topic](#)^c**hasSkype**^{dp}back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasSkype>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Skype account of user contacts

has super-propertiestop data property^{dp}**has domain**[Person](#)^c**hasStatus**^{dp}back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasStatus>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Possible status of the smart device

has super-propertiestop data property^{dp}**has domain**[SmartDevice](#)^c**hasTablet-view**^{dp}back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasTablet-view>**is defined by**<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Confirmation to be shown on the robot's tablet

has super-propertiestop data property^{dp}**has domain**[Goal](#)^c

hasTelegram^{dp}

[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasTelegram>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Telegram account of user's contact accounts

has super-properties

[top data property^{dp}](#)

has domain

[Person^c](#)

hasType^{dp}

[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasType>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Type of the smart devices (device - sensor)

has super-properties

[top data property^{dp}](#)

has domain

[SmartDevice^c](#)

hasUDDL^{dp}

[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasUDDL>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

UDDL file describing the operator

has super-properties

[top data property^{dp}](#)

has domain

[Operator^c](#)

hasURL^{dp}

[back to ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasURL>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

youtube URL of the video

has super-properties

top data property^{dp}

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

[hasUrl-article^{dp}](#)

back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasUrl-article>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Webpage for the ReadNewsAction

has super-properties

top data property^{dp}

has domain

[TVChannel^c](#)

[hasUrl-root^{dp}](#)

back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasUrl-root>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

Webpage for the readnews action

has super-properties

top data property^{dp}

has domain

[TVChannel^c](#)

[hasValue^{dp}](#)

back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#hasValue>

is defined by

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology>

String value for handling triggering and necessary conditions

has super-properties

top data property^{dp}

has domain

[Topic^c](#)

Annotation Properties

[comment](#) [creator](#) [description](#) [is defined by](#) [issued](#) [label](#) [language](#) [license](#)
[modified](#) [preferred namespace prefix](#) [preferred namespace uri](#) [rights](#)
[term status](#) [title](#) [version info](#)

comment^{ap}

back to [ToC](#) or [Annotation Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#comment>

creator^{ap}

back to [ToC](#) or [Annotation Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/creator>

description^{ap}

back to [ToC](#) or [Annotation Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/description>

is defined by^{ap}

back to [ToC](#) or [Annotation Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#isDefinedBy>

issued^{ap}

back to [ToC](#) or [Annotation Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/issued>

label^{ap}

back to [ToC](#) or [Annotation Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#label>

language^{ap}

back to [ToC](#) or [Annotation Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/language>

license^{ap}

back to [ToC](#) or [Annotation Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://creativecommons.org/ns#license>

modified^{ap}

back to [ToC](#) or [Annotation Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/modified>

preferred namespace prefix^{ap}

back to [ToC](#) or [Annotation Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://purl.org/vocab/vann/preferredNamespacePrefix>

preferred namespace uri^{ap}

back to [ToC](#) or [Annotation Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://purl.org/vocab/vann/preferredNamespaceUri>

rights^{ap}

back to [ToC](#) or [Annotation Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/rights>

term status^{ap}

back to [ToC](#) or [Annotation Property ToC](#)

IRI: http://www.w3.org/2003/06/sw-vocab-status/ns#term_status

title^{ap}

back to [ToC](#) or [Annotation Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/title>

version info^{ap}

back to [ToC](#) or [Annotation Property ToC](#)

IRI: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#versionInfo>

Namespace Declarations

back to [ToC](#)

default namespace

<http://caressesrobot.org/ontology#>

22-rdf-syntax-ns

<http://w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>

caressesrobot-org

<http://caressesrobot.org/>

cc

<http://creativecommons.org/ns#>

dc

<http://purl.org/dc/terms/>

foaf

<http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/>

language

<http://publications.europa.eu/resource/authority/language/>

owl

<http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#>

rdf

<http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>

rdf-schema

<http://w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>

rdfs

<http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>

swrla

<http://swrl.stanford.edu/ontologies/3.3/swrla.owl#>

vann

<http://purl.org/vocab/vann/>

vs

<http://www.w3.org/2003/06/sw-vocab-status/ns#>

xmlschema

<http://w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>

xsd

<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>

This HTML document was partially obtained by processing the OWL ontology source code through [LODE](#), *Live OWL Documentation Environment*, developed by [Silvio Peroni](#).